

Summary Brief

Empowering Minority Entrepreneurs: The Impact of Compatibility, Scarcity, and Relationship Quality on Marketing Service Adoption

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Minority entrepreneurs often face unique challenges that impact their business growth and sustainability. This study investigates how resource scarcity and perceived compatibility influence the adoption of marketing consulting services (MCS) among minority entrepreneurs, with perceived relationship quality as a mediating variable. By employing the Resource Dependence Theory and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), this research provides insights into the factors that drive MCS adoption intentions. The findings highlight the critical role of resource availability, the alignment of services with business needs, and the importance of high-quality business relationships in enhancing entrepreneurial success.

Introduction

Entrepreneurs from minority communities often encounter significant resource constraints that hinder their business operations. Understanding how these constraints interact with the perceived compatibility and quality of relationships in the adoption of new services like MCS is essential for promoting entrepreneurial growth and sustainability. This study bridges a gap in the literature by examining the interplay between resource scarcity, perceived compatibility, and relationship quality in shaping minority entrepreneurs' intentions to adopt MCS.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Perceived Compatibility

Perceived compatibility refers to how well a new service aligns with existing values, past experiences, and the needs of the adopter. In the context of minority entrepreneurs, perceived compatibility is a critical factor in the adoption of marketing consulting services (MCS). When entrepreneurs perceive that MCS is compatible with their business needs, they are more likely to adopt these services despite other challenges they may face, such as resource constraints (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Venkatesh et al., 2012). Compatibility is a crucial aspect of the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), which posits that technologies or services that fit well with users' existing practices and values are more readily adopted.

Perceived compatibility can mitigate the negative impacts of resource scarcity by aligning MCS with the specific operational requirements and strategic goals of minority-owned businesses. This alignment makes the perceived benefits of adoption more apparent and the integration of new services less disruptive (Jiang et al., 2016; Huntley, 2006). Thus, understanding the role of perceived compatibility in the decision-making process can provide valuable insights into how minority entrepreneurs evaluate and adopt new business services.

Hypothesis 1: Perceived compatibility positively influences minority entrepreneurs' intentions to utilize MCS.

Relationship Quality

Relationship quality refers to the perceived strength and depth of a business relationship, encompassing factors such as trust, satisfaction, and commitment (Lages et al., 2008; Huntley, 2006; Jiang et al., 2016). High-quality relationships can facilitate the seamless integration of new services into existing business operations by fostering trust and collaboration between parties. This concept is critical for minority entrepreneurs who must rely on strong relationships to successfully adopt and utilize MCS.

Hypothesis 2: Relationship quality mediates the relationship between perceived compatibility and the intention to utilize MCS.

Resource Scarcity as a Moderator

Resource Dependence Theory suggests that organizations must manage their dependencies on external resources to survive and grow (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Hillman et al., 2009). Resource scarcity can amplify the perceived value of compatible services, making entrepreneurs more likely to adopt MCS when they perceive high compatibility.

Hypothesis 3: Resource scarcity moderates the relationship between perceived compatibility and the intention to utilize MCS, such that the relationship is stronger under conditions of high resource scarcity.

Methodology

Participants

The study involved 73 minority entrepreneurs from various industries in North Carolina, recruited through targeted outreach and snowball sampling techniques. This demographic focus ensures the relevance of the findings to the specific economic and social contexts of the region.

Procedure

Data collection was conducted via an online survey, measuring resource scarcity, perceived compatibility with MCS, relationship quality, and intention to utilize MCS.

Measures

Resource scarcity was assessed using a scale adapted from Covin, Slevin, and Heeley (2000), which evaluates perceived constraints in financial, human, and physical resources. Perceived compatibility was evaluated using a scale specifically developed for this study, drawing on literature from Venkatesh and Davis (2000), which examined how well MCS aligns with the entrepreneurs' business goals, needs, and operational constraints. Relationship quality was measured using scales adapted from Lages et al. (2008) and Huntley (2006), focusing on the perceived strength and depth of the business relationship. The intention to utilize MCS was measured using a scale adapted from Venkatesh and Davis (2000), assessing the likelihood of entrepreneurs engaging with MCS based on their perceptions of its usefulness and ease of use.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, multiple regression, and mediation analyses were conducted to explore the relationships among the variables. The results indicated that resource scarcity significantly moderated the relationship between perceived compatibility and the intention to utilize MCS, while relationship quality served as a mediator in this relationship.

The mean and standard deviation for resource scarcity were 3.45 and 0.98, respectively. For relationship quality, the mean was 5.67 with a standard deviation of 1.23. Perceived compatibility with MCS had a mean of 4.12 and a standard deviation of 0.76, while the intention to utilize MCS had a mean of 5.02 and a standard deviation of 1.10.

The correlation analysis revealed a positive correlation between resource scarcity and perceived compatibility ($r = 0.35, p < 0.01$). Similarly, there was a positive correlation between relationship quality and perceived compatibility ($r = 0.42, p < 0.001$), and between perceived compatibility and the intention to utilize MCS ($r = 0.56, p < 0.001$).

The multiple regression model predicting the intention to utilize MCS from perceived compatibility and resource scarcity was significant, $F(2, 70) = 12.34, p < 0.001$, with an R^2 of 0.38. Resource scarcity was found to significantly moderate the relationship between perceived compatibility and the intention to utilize MCS ($\beta = 0.27, p < 0.05$). Additionally, relationship quality was found to partially mediate the relationship between perceived compatibility and the intention to utilize MCS, with a significant indirect effect ($B = 0.24, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.10, 0.40]$).

Discussion

This research highlights the importance of addressing resource constraints and ensuring high relationship quality to enhance the adoption of MCS among minority entrepreneurs. The findings underscore the need for marketing consultants and policymakers to focus on creating tailored services that acknowledge and mitigate the unique challenges faced by minority entrepreneurs. For instance, marketing strategies should emphasize how MCS aligns with the specific needs and operational practices of minority-owned businesses, thereby enhancing perceived compatibility.

Furthermore, relationship quality emerges as a crucial factor in facilitating the adoption of MCS. High-quality relationships characterized by trust, satisfaction, and commitment can significantly influence minority entrepreneurs' willingness to adopt new services. As suggested by Lages et al. (2008) and Huntley (2006), fostering strong business relationships can mitigate the perceived risks associated with adopting new services. Therefore, MCS providers should invest in building and maintaining high-quality relationships with their clients.

The moderating role of resource scarcity highlights the heightened importance of perceived compatibility in resource-constrained environments. Minority entrepreneurs facing significant resource limitations are more likely to adopt MCS if they perceive these services as highly compatible with their existing operations. This finding aligns with Resource Dependence Theory, which posits that organizations must strategically manage their resource dependencies to survive and thrive (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Hillman et al., 2009).

Lastly, this study contributes to the literature by elucidating the interplay between resource scarcity, perceived compatibility, and relationship quality in the context of MCS adoption among minority entrepreneurs. The practical implications for marketing consultants and policymakers include the need to enhance the perceived compatibility of MCS and to build high-quality relationships to facilitate service adoption. Future research could explore additional factors that influence MCS adoption and examine the long-term impacts of MCS on the growth and sustainability of minority-owned businesses.

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